

Transport Properties of Binary Mixtures of *N*-Methylcyclohexylamine with Benzene, Toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Xylenes at 303.15 K

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Viscosities for binary liquid mixtures of *N*-methylcyclohexylamine with benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes were measured at 303.15 K. In case of excess of viscosity (η^E) the values are positive for all the systems over the entire range of composition. The study was extended to evaluate interaction parameter (d), interaction energy (W_{vis}) and Gibbs free energy for activation of flow (G^E)

A number of workers¹⁻³ have utilised the direct approach developed by Grunberg and Nissan⁴ and Katti and Chaudhari⁵ to estimate the strength of interactions in binary mixtures of non-electrolytes from viscosity data. The present paper forms a part of our programme on the measurement of thermodynamic properties of non-electrolyte solutions containing *N*-methylcyclohexylamine as a common component. We report here new experimental data for excess viscosities of the systems: *N*-methylcyclohexylamine + benzene, +toluene, + *o*-xylene, + *m*-xylene and + *p*-xylene.

Results and Discussion

The values of density and viscosity of pure components are included in Table 1. For the five binary systems the excess viscosity curves were determined at 303.15 K. The experimental data are reported in Table 2 and presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Mole fraction of *N*-methylcyclohexylamine: (O) benzene, (●) toluene, (Δ) *o*-xylene, (▲) *m*-xylene and (×) *p*-xylene.

Excess viscosity (η^E) at each composition is obtained from the relation suggested by Fort and Moore⁶,

$$\eta^E = \eta_m - [x_1 \eta_1 + (x_2) \eta_2] \quad (1)$$

where η_m is the viscosity of the mixture and η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of *N*-methylcyclohexylamine and non-common component respectively.

Excess Gibbs free energy for activation of flow (G^E) was calculated using Eyring relation⁷,

$$G^E = RT[\ln \eta V - x_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 - (x_2) \ln \eta_2 V_2] \quad (2)$$

Grunberg and Nissan⁴ formulated the following expression to define the interaction parameter (d),

$$d = \frac{1}{x_1(x_2)} [\ln \eta - x_1 \ln \eta_1 - (x_2) \ln \eta_2] \quad (3)$$

Katti and Chaudhari⁵ deduced the following expression to show the variation of viscosity with molar volume and composition,

$$W_{vis} = \frac{RT}{x_1(x_2)} [\ln \eta V - x \ln \eta_1 V_1 - (x_2) \ln \eta_2 V_2] \quad (4)$$

where W_{vis} represents the interaction energy between the components.

The excess viscosity (η^E) dependence on composition can be expressed by an empirical equation,

$$\eta^E = x_1(x_2)[a_0 + a_1(x_1 - x_2) + a_2(x_1 - x_2)^2] \quad (5)$$

where a_0 , a_1 and a_2 are adjustable parameters.

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND VISCOSITY DATA OF PURE COMPONENTS AT 303.15 K

Component	ρ (g cm ⁻³)		η (cp)	
	Exptl.	Lit.*	Exptl.	Lit.*
<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine	0.846 87	—	1.216 7	—
Benzene	0.868 46	0.868 49	0.568 5	0.569 0
Toluene	0.857 64	0.857 70	0.526 2	0.526 0
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.871 55	0.871 60	0.692 4	0.692 7
<i>m</i> -Xylene	0.855 49	0.855 51	0.546 2	0.546 1
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.852 25	0.852 30	0.567 3	0.568 0

*Refs. 9 and 10.

The standard deviation $\sigma(\eta^E)$ is calculated using the equation,

$$\sigma(\eta^E) = \left[\frac{\sum(\eta_{\text{obs}}^E - \eta_{\text{cal}}^E)^2}{n-p} \right]^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where n and p are the number of observed results and the parameters respectively. The values of the parameters obtained by least-square method

TABLE 2—MOLE FRACTION (x_1), DENSITY (ρ), VISCOSITY OF MIXTURE (η_m), EXCESS VISCOSITY (η^E), EXCESS GIBBS FREE ENERGY FOR ACTIVATION OF FLOW (G^E), STRENGTH OF INTERACTION PARAMETER (d) AND INTERACTION ENERGY (W_{visc}) AT 303.15 K

x_1	ρ g cm ⁻³	η_m cp	G^E cal mol ⁻¹	d	W_{visc} cal mol ⁻¹
<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine + Benzene					
0.000 0	0.868 46	0.568 5	—	—	—
0.108 9	0.864 63	0.670 1	25.7	0.353	264.8
0.174 5	0.862 44	0.730 6	36.7	0.338	254.9
0.407 9	0.855 87	0.934 9	54.7	0.692	529.6
0.453 0	0.854 84	0.971 1	54.9	0.292	221.8
0.611 9	0.851 52	1.081 1	49.2	0.268	207.2
0.705 2	0.849 92	1.133 6	41.5	0.257	199.5
0.758 8	0.849 17	1.158 4	35.7	0.251	195.2
0.853 3	0.848 10	1.191 6	23.6	0.272	212.0
1.000 0	0.846 87	1.216 7	—	—	—
<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine + Toluene					
0.000 0	0.857 64	0.526 2	—	—	—
0.166 6	0.855 75	0.700 2	74.5	0.865	536.3
0.255 8	0.854 53	0.781 8	100.0	0.847	525.4
0.433 3	0.851 97	0.926 4	103.2	0.673	420.2
0.503 8	0.851 00	0.978 1	105.8	0.679	423.3
0.539 7	0.890 52	1.003 9	107.0	0.692	430.9
0.685 9	0.848 76	1.095 8	98.1	0.733	455.5
0.742 7	0.848 21	1.127 0	97.7	1.058	516.5
0.883 1	0.847 15	1.189 0	48.2	0.751	467.2
1.000 0	0.846 87	1.216 7	—	—	—
<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine + <i>o</i> -Xylene					
0.000 0	0.871 55	0.692 4	—	—	—
0.126 2	0.867 67	0.891 6	10.9	-0.007	98.9
0.185 7	0.866 00	0.969 8	185.0	2.027	1 223.6
0.283 7	0.863 13	1.075 2	180.9	1.474	890.4
0.459 3	0.858 10	1.181 2	142.9	0.951	575.4
0.548 5	0.855 70	1.200 0	120.1	0.801	484.9
0.679 0	0.852 48	1.195 6	88.9	0.627	407.7
0.771 3	0.850 37	1.180 8	54.1	0.558	312.3
0.926 8	0.847 78	1.187 3	13.4	0.325	197.9
1.000 0	0.846 87	1.216 7	—	—	—
<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine + <i>m</i> -Xylene					
0.000 0	0.855 49	0.546 2	—	—	—
0.195 2	0.853 39	0.848 1	-89.8	-0.952	-571.8
0.392 4	0.851 39	1.003 3	109.5	0.871	459.3
0.464 3	0.850 73	1.049 5	107.6	0.715	432.5
0.538 0	0.850 02	1.088 9	176.9	1.179	711.7
0.590 6	0.849 56	1.114 2	176.5	1.216	729.9
0.632 3	0.849 22	1.133 2	160.7	1.145	691.2
0.777 9	0.848 11	1.190 8	95.9	0.919	555.3
0.890 1	0.847 42	1.218 0	45.7	0.769	466.7
1.000 0	0.846 87	1.216 7	—	—	—
<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine + <i>p</i> -Xylene					
0.000 0	0.852 25	0.567 3	—	—	—
0.194 2	0.852 05	0.712 4	57.6	0.403	240.2
0.250 8	0.851 75	0.754 2	52.5	0.462	279.6
0.348 3	0.851 05	0.804 1	67.2	0.488	295.8
0.384 9	0.850 71	0.845 3	56.1	0.391	236.8
0.613 9	0.848 63	0.985 0	48.9	0.340	206.5
0.626 2	0.848 49	0.992 0	48.1	0.339	205.4
0.801 5	0.847 26	1.092 8	25.2	0.260	158.2
0.846 9	0.874 04	1.120 3	20.1	0.255	154.9
1.000 0	0.846 87	1.216 7	—	—	—

are included in Table 3 alongwith the standard deviation. The values of η^E which refers to the deviation from rectilinear dependence^{1,5} of viscosity of mixture on composition (x_1) can be discussed from the viewpoint of inter-molecular interactions^{1,6}. Specific interactions such as dipole-dipole interactions and existence of charge transfer and hydrogen bond leading to the formation of complex species between the unlike molecules of the components tend to make the value of η^E positive. The η^E values are positive in all the systems studied which may be ascribed to the presence of specific dipole-dipole type interactions. This suggests that the effect of interaction between unlike molecules on viscosity is greater than that due to the dissociation of polar molecules. The algebraic values of η^E for all the systems fall in the order: *p*-xylene < toluene < benzene < *m*-xylene < *o*-xylene.

The sign and magnitude of interaction parameters (d) would depend on the type of molecular interactions and difference in size and shape of the unlike molecules. The variation of d with composition is not large except where strong specific interaction might be expected at any given composition the variation of d is similar to that of η^E being increasingly positive as the strength of interaction increases. The d -values for the title systems run parallel with η^E values. The interaction energy parameter (W_{visc}) run parallel with d -values. The values of excess Gibbs free energy for activation of flow (G^E) (Table 2) suggest that the behaviour of the systems is in line with the observation made by Reed and Taylor⁸.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF PARAMETERS IN EQUATION (5) AND STANDARD DEVIATION $\sigma(\eta^E)$ AT 303.15 K

<i>N</i> -Methylcyclohexylamine + Component	a_0	a_1	a_2	$\sigma(\eta^E)$
Benzene	0.454	0.162	-0.016	0.000 3
Toluene	0.416	0.050	0.095	0.000 2
<i>o</i> -Xylene	0.951	-0.629	-0.389	0.000 4
<i>m</i> -Xylene	0.751	-0.300	0.412	0.000 3
<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.102	-0.078	-0.061	0.000 1

Experimental

Viscosity was determined at 303.15 K by using Ubbelohde viscometers (accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$). The accuracy of viscosity was checked by measuring the viscosity of pure benzene and cyclohexane. The results agree within $\pm 0.5\%$ with those reported in the literature^{9,10}. Mixtures of various compositions were prepared by weight. A constant volume of the mixture was transferred to the viscometer and then inserted into a thermostat controlled at 303.15 ± 0.01 K. The viscosity was computed from flow time (t), density (ρ) and the constant of the viscometer (K) using the equation,

$$\eta = K\rho t$$

Densities of pure components were determined using a pycnometer. In the case of mixtures, densities were obtained from excess volumes^{9,11} using the relation,

$$\rho = \frac{x_1 M_1 + (x_2) M_2}{V^0 + V^E}$$

where x_1 and x_2 stand for mole fractions and M_1 and M_2 for the molecular weights of *N*-methylcyclohexylamine and the non-common component respectively, and V^0 and V^E for the ideal molar volume and excess molar volume respectively.

All the chemicals were purified by the reported methods⁹. *N*-Methylcyclohexylamine (Fluka AG, 99% GC pure) was used as such. Benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes (all B.D.H.) were fractionally distilled. All the compounds were dried over activated molecular sieves. The purity of the samples was checked by measuring density and refractive index. Refractive index was determined with an Abbe's refractometer (accuracy ± 0.0002).

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